

Functioning of the Rain Gardens

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to explore the feasibility and potential benefits of using treated CWWTP effluent for irrigating plants in an urban environment. Four irrigation boxes were set up to assess plant growth and health using different water sources, including river water and treated effluent. Water quality, trace elements, microbiological parameters, and micropollutants were monitored over two seasons. The results demonstrated the viability of using treated effluent for irrigation, as water quality parameters remained within legislative limits, and plant growth and health showed no significant differences between the boxes. Nutrient levels in the treated effluent were higher than in river water, benefiting plant growth. Accumulation of trace elements and micropollutants in plants was minimal and deemed negligible for non-edible plants. In conclusion, the study showed that treated effluent can be a sustainable alternative to conventional drinking water uptake for irrigation, contributing to a more environmentally friendly approach to urban water management.

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1 Executive summary

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of the impacts of using different water sources for irrigation, including untreated river water, effluent, and effluent treated with ultraviolet (UV) and ultrafiltration (UF/UV) technologies. For this purpose, four irrigation boxes were built on the premises of the Central Wastewater Treatment Plant (CWWTP) in Prague. Being a part of the Wider-Uptake project, this undertaking focused on overcoming barriers related to monitoring and control of health and quality risks, circular economy and efficiency potential, governance and business models for industrial symbiosis, and measuring water smartness and progress towards Sustainable Development Goals. The study monitors various parameters over a two-year period, assessing water quality, plant growth and health, and soil quality.

Water quality evaluation revealed that most parameters remained within the legislative limits for all water types. Although the effluent showed slightly higher biological oxygen demand (BOD₅) levels than river water, these levels did not exceed the legal limits. The chemical oxygen demand (COD_{Cr}) and total suspended solids (TSS) values also complied with the legislative limits. River water displayed significantly lower conductivity, dissolved inorganic salts, and specific ions, which can potentially lead to soil salinization. Trace elements were generally below the legislative limits, except for cadmium (Cd) and chromium (Cr). Tertiary treatment did not consistently affect micropollutant content.

In terms of plant growth and health, no significant differences were observed among the four boxes, except for grass treated with effluent, which had parasites in the second season. Trace element analyses revealed varying concentrations in plants depending on the water source. Accumulation of micropollutants in plants was slightly higher when irrigated with effluents, but the levels were still considered low and the associated risk negligible.

Soil quality analysis demonstrated that after the second irrigation season, the soil exhibited lower concentrations of various parameters, including trace elements, due to being washed down to the filtrate. Micropollutants were detected at levels measured in units of ug/kg of dry matter, with tramadol being the most prevalent. Soil pH and hummus content remained relatively unchanged, while microbial activity exhibited some shifts. Salinity was higher in the soil irrigated with effluent, although this was considered a worst-case scenario due to the use of roofs.

Additionally, all of the processed data, including the snapshots of the plants throughout the project, was aggregated in a human-friendly readable format on a database connected to a Wider-Uptake web application (<https://database.wider-uptake.eu/>). For now, this application allows the participants of the project to work with the data more efficiently, but the outlook is bright for the use of similar applications in practice outside of research activities.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the implications of using different water sources for irrigation. While there were some variations in water quality, plant growth, and soil composition, the use of effluents for irrigation can still be considered a viable and sustainable option, provided that proper monitoring and management practices are employed.

2 Recapitulation: Goals of the Project

2.1 Wider-Uptake

This report covers a part of the WIDER UPTAKE project. WIDER UPTAKE is a H2020 project that aims to facilitate industrial symbiosis as a mean to increase resource efficiency, limit emissions and develop sustainable business based on water-smart solutions. The project's hypothesis is that the barriers for wider uptake of water-smart solutions are not only technological but also of organizational, regulatory, social, and economic character.

WIDER UPTAKE will identify and demonstrate common measures to overcome barriers related to:

1. 'Monitoring and control of health and quality risks'
2. 'Circular-economy and efficiency potential'
3. 'Governance and business models for industrial symbiosis'
4. 'Measuring water smartness and progress towards SDG'.

The project includes demonstrations at five different locations/countries/settings of:

- Wastewater reuse for agriculture and urban greening
- Phosphorus recycling, biogas and biochar utilisation
- Production of biocomposites for manufacturing materials with resources recovered from the whole water cycle.

The partnership in WIDER UPTAKE includes 11 water utilities and industries and 7 research institutes or universities, distributed across 5 countries (Norway, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Italy and Ghana).

2.2 Irrigation Boxes

Irrigation boxes were used in the project to simulate the irrigation of different botanical arrangements with recovered water. The biomass used was comprised of

- lawn grass,
- plants and flowers, and
- bushes and shrubs.

All of these were present in all the four boxes (Figure 1), which were, consequently, irrigated with four types of recovered water:

- **River water from Vltava:** this water was used for comparison with the effluent, as it is commonly used for irrigation of urban and agricultural areas in the Czech Republic.

- **NWL¹effluent:** obtained effluent is after biological stage of CWWTP (secondary clarifier and phosphorus post-precipitation), simulating the direct use of the effluent for irrigation without any further treatment.
- **UV²-treated NWL effluent:** UV light is used as a disinfection method and should ensure microbial safety of the water without negative effect on plants.
- **NWL effluent treated with UV and UF³:** ultrafiltration shall provide treatment of bigger impurities, lowering TSS content and turbidity. Since UV efficiency decreases with higher turbidity/TSS content, we assume that ultrafiltration pretreatment would increase UV efficiency.

Figure 1 Irrigation boxes at the CWWTP

These containers were assembled with the following goals in mind.

2.2.1 Demonstration of safety of use

Recycled water is one of the pillars of the Circular Economy. Its sustainable extraction from wastewater and subsequent incorporation in a city water management strategy is the ultimate goal of the initiative. However, one of the obstacles of implementing recovered water solutions is a lack of acceptance in our societies.

¹ NVL (from Czech Nová vodní linka - 'New Water Line') is the newly constructed Central Wastewater Treatment Plant in Prague, Czech Republic

² Ultraviolet disinfection

³ Ultrafiltration

The irrigation boxes offer to break the mold of public nonacceptance by demonstrating safe use of reclaimed water in action. They do so by providing visual confirmation of plants growing on cameras on the one hand and by thorough chemical monitoring and analyses on the other. While the healthy plants assure people that the water is suitable for irrigation purposes, the results of monitoring and testing serve as a proof of safety.

2.2.2 Development of monitoring and control systems for risk assessment purposes

As there is an increasing concern about human health and effect on the environment with micropollutants, persistent compounds and CMR (cancerous, mutagenic and toxic for reproduction) chemicals, the recycled water cannot be used without undergoing a proper risk assessment procedure. That is why the irrigation boxes were equipped with various sensors and were consistently probed and analyzed in a whole layer of the soil, as well as samples were regularly taken for the two-year period and laboratory tested for a wide range of parameters to identify potential threats. The implementation of this control and monitoring system is therefore crucial in ensuring the safe and effective use of recycled water in urban areas.

This control and monitoring system had to be tested out and partially automated on the data coming from the irrigation boxes.

2.2.3 Quantifying the increase in resource efficiency and economic benefits

The tests carried out on the irrigation boxes and the whole of the experiment needed to highlight the benefits of using recycled water compared to drinking water. One way to do it is to quantify the increase in resource efficiency. The foundation for it would be an experimental determination of the minimum quality of the water source that is needed to safely irrigate parks and recreation areas. That is why four types of water were examined in irrigation boxes experiment.

2.2.4 Preparing water for irrigation purposes

The final purpose of the irrigation boxes was to carry out and describe the process of preparing water for irrigation purposes. A container with water preparation and measurement equipment was installed on site and the necessary technologies were optimized under the professional technological surveillance throughout the whole project (Figure 2). Most importantly, there were an UF module and UV lamps installed (Figure 3, Figure 4).

Figure 2 Water Treatment Container Interior

Figure 3 Ultrafiltration module

Figure 4 UV lamp

The CWWTP's effluent did not undergo any additional treatment process.

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3 Demonstration Units

3.1 Overview

Four demonstration units were constructed as planned and placed on CWWTP's premises. As per "3D printed rain garden boxes" report, the beds of the boxes were manufactured on an industrial-scale 3D printer, filled with the gravel layer and appropriate soil for growth media and equipped with sprinkler irrigation system (Figure 5). Furthermore, the boxes were fitted out with a camera system, flowmeters and temperature and humidity sensors (both in soil and near boxes for air humidity) that preprocessed and provided the data to the Horizon2020 database application.

Figure 5 Irrigation system in the boxes

Aside from these units, a container with water preparation equipment was put together as presented in the aforementioned report.

3.2 Design and Construction Process

The design and construction process for the experimental irrigation boxes aimed to ensure the uniformity and reliability of the experiment. To accomplish this, identical boxes were constructed using high-quality, durable materials capable of withstanding varying weather conditions and supporting the plants throughout the growth period. The boxes were designed with dimensions of 4.5 m x 1.5 m, divided into three sections, each measuring 1.5 m x 1.5 m. The division of compartments allowed the comparison of the influence of different water sources on various selected plant types. A support structure was built for the boxes to provide stability and facilitate the installation of necessary equipment described in chapter 6 of this report. To ensure the proper insulation and survival of the plants through colder autumn and

winter periods, the walls of the boxes were laid out with polystyrene layer. The water sources were prepared according to the flow diagram and measurement scheme for the water treatment processes inside the pilot-scale container unit near the boxes, ensuring consistent inlet water quality.

The floor of the boxes was 3D printed in a way that allowed for compartmentalization of soil layers and biomass (i.e., vertically and horizontally) (Figure 6 and Figure 7). The reason for this division is to monitor the quality of the filtrate as well as the irrigation water in soil and to assess the effect of the irrigation water on plants.

Figure 6 The floor of the boxes during construction

Figure 7 Layers and composition of the boxes

3.3 Growth Media and Plant Selection

The growth media and plant selection for the irrigation boxes aimed to provide a representative sample of plants typically found in urban environments while also ensuring the plants' ability to tolerate different water sources. Since plant kinds are specific in their behavior, e.g. this tendency to accumulate different types of pollutants, three sections of plants were selected to represent the most commonly present plants in urban parks. The soil used in all boxes was consistent in composition, which allowed for a controlled comparison of the water sources' effects on plant and soil health.

For the lawn area, a park-type carpeted lawn was chosen due to its durability. This type of lawn is commonly found in parks and gardens, making it a suitable choice for the experiment.

The plants selected for the boxes included a variety of perennials, chosen for their diverse growth characteristics and adaptability to different environmental conditions. The selected perennials included *Geranium sanguineum* "Ankum's Pride", *Hemerocallis* "Stella D'oro", *Salvia nemorosa* "Caradonna", *Echinacea purpurea* "Primadonna Deep Rose", *Coreopsis verticillata* "Grandiflora", and *Heuchera sanguinea* "Leuchtkäfer".

The shrubs selected for the experiment were chosen for their ability to grow under various environmental conditions and their prevalence in urban landscapes. These included *Ulmus pumila*, *Carpinus betulus*, and *Ligustrum vulgare* "Lodense". The chosen plants were spaced appropriately to ensure optimal growth and facilitate the comparison of the different water sources' effects on their development (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Flowers' segment of the irrigation box

4 Water Sources and transportation to Treatment Processes and irrigation

This chapter provides an overview of the water sources and treatment processes used in the irrigation experiment. All sources for transportation to the technological containment and irrigation are taken in location CWWTP Prague - New Water Line (NWL):

- 1) Vltava river (sampling point was above the effluent outlet, and therefore before mixing the Vltava river with effluent from NWL)
- 2) Effluent from NWL (for second irrigation season, effluent was taken after tertiary treatment in rondel) (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Transport to technological containment for accumulation and irrigation (Vltava river and effluent from NWL) or for treatment process, accumulation and irrigation (treated effluent from NWL with UV and with Ultrafiltration and UV process).

Transportation in this scenario consists of the efficient pumping of liquid at a rate of approximately 0.5 liters per second into an Intermediate Bulk Container (IBC) and transporting it to the site using a car (Figure 10). This process is designed to be time-effective, with the objective of filling a 1 cubic meter IBC container in an estimated 30 minutes. The combination of a rapid pumping rate and a sizable storage capacity ensures that the transportation process remains both manageable and streamlined for optimal results.

Figure 10 A car with an IBC container for transportation

Transportation distance was approximately 2.4 km for Vltava River intake point and 1.7 km for effluent intake point in NWL (Figure 11).

Figure 11 Map of CWWTP including NWL

Following the transportation phase, a secondary pumping process is required to transfer the contents into designated accumulation boxes. These boxes serve as an essential step in the

treatment processes, housed within a technological containment facility, and are also utilized for irrigation purposes. This additional pumping stage ensures that the transferred materials are effectively managed and appropriately allocated for their intended applications, ultimately contributing to a streamlined and efficient system (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Pumping the water into irrigation containers at the site

4.1 Box 1: Vltava River Water

Box 1 was irrigated using water sourced directly from the Vltava River before mixing with effluent from NWL (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Vltava river water uptake

4.2 Box 2: Treated Effluent from CWWTP — New Water Line (NWL)

Box 2 utilized treated effluent from the end of the biological stage combined with the tertiary treatment process in NWL.

The biological treatment process involves the use of various microorganisms to break down and remove organic pollutants from the wastewater. This stage of treatment is crucial in reducing the organic load in the effluent and improving water quality.

The main goal of the tertiary treatment process at NWL is to achieve low phosphorous and suspended solids concentrations in the effluent from NWL by Densadeg 2D technology (lamellar sedimentation tanks with possibility of chemical post-precipitation).

During the first irrigation season, the effluent was pumped at the outlet canal from WWTP to the river. However, WWTP implemented UV treatment of the effluent. Therefore, before the second irrigation season, the pumps were moved for taking water after Densadeg 2D process. (Figure 14)

Figure 14 NWL effluent uptake on the premises: (1) Service of the pump used for the uptake, (2) preparation of the pump at the site and (3) installation of the pipe in the Densadeg 2D tank

4.3 Box 3: Treated Effluent from CWWTP – NWL with UV disinfection

After the transportation, the treated effluent from the CWWTP's biological stage placed in the IBC container was pumped to the pilot-plant unit and underwent an additional treatment process, ultraviolet (UV) disinfection. This process uses UV light to inactivate pathogenic microorganisms, such as bacteria, viruses, and protozoa, making the water safer for irrigation purposes. Used UV lamp was Aquada Maxima 2 with maximum flow 1.85 m³/h. After the treatment in pilot-plant unit, the water was pumped to the accumulation tank and subsequently, was used for irrigation of Box 3.

4.4 Box 4: Treated Effluent from CWWTP – NWL with Ultrafiltration and UV disinfection (advanced treatment processes)

Box 4 received water that underwent ultrafiltration process, with aim to reduce TSS and turbidity, and consequently, this water underwent UV treatment by the second UV lamp Aquada Maxima 2 operated under same conditions as UV lamp for the Box 3, to ensure the highest level of water quality for irrigation. Ultrafiltration membrane used was HYDRAcap® MAX 40 with pore size 0.08 um and maximum feed pressure 5 bar.

After the evaluation of the first irrigation season, the by-pass of accumulation tank after UF was implemented before second irrigation season to avoid secondary contamination from the tank used as a membrane backwash (Figure 15).

Figure 15 New piping arrangement for by-passing the accumulation tank after UF and the by-pass system itself

5 Experiment Results and Analysis

Sampling of the irrigation water was done every two weeks to measure basic physico-chemical parameters and microbial parameters. Once a month, the trace elements (incl. heavy metals) concentrations and micropollutants content were monitored in the irrigation waters. For all of the parameters, filtrate from the boxes was sampled once a month as well.

Micropollutants in solid samples (soil and plant biomass) were monitored before the start of the experiment and then at the end of every irrigation season. Metals in solid samples were measured at the start, the middle and the end of every season. Bacterial activities had specific sampling plan since at the beginning, the change of the activities was expected to change more often due to the shock of the system. Therefore, at the beginning, the samples for the bacterial activity in soil were taken every few days, then every week, every two weeks, and when equilibrium was reached, every month. For microbial activities, two depths (0-25 and 25-45 cm) were monitored. In total, over 500 soil samples were taken only for the monitoring of the bacterial activities in soil.

Soil was sampled by special sampling device through the whole depth.

The selection of appropriate parameters for water, soil and plant quality monitoring is critical for assessing the potential risks associated with recycled water usage. Several criteria were considered for parameter selection for monitoring, including legislative requirements, environmental relevance, and potential health risks. By carefully selecting parameters, it is possible to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the water quality and potential environmental and health impacts.

Certain parameters, such as BOD₅, COD_{Cr}, or microorganisms cultivated at 36 °C, provide general information about the water sample and about its impurity. These parameters are non-specific and are commonly used in water quality monitoring. Moreover, BOD₅ and TSS are being restricted by European regulations. Heavy metals were selected due to their potential for bioaccumulation and possible chronic toxicity, and some trace elements, such as Cu or Zn, were selected due to their toxicity at high concentrations and importance at low concentrations for plant prosperity. Conductivity, TDS, DIS, and specific ions were selected as parameters for potential soil salinization assessment. Microbial parameters were selected based on European and Czech regulations, focusing on more persistent species present in wastewater which might be more resistant to disinfection. Bacterial activities in soil are commonly evaluated to assess the impact of environmental factors, such as fertilizers or pesticides. As wastewater can contain substances that affect bacterial activity in soil, monitoring these parameters is crucial.

In the scientific community, there are still many unanswered questions about micropollutants in the environment. Although these pollutants are not limited in wastewater reuse regulations or irrigation regulations, monitoring them can provide valuable information about their fate in the environment and potential impacts on the food cycle.

Overall, selecting appropriate parameters for water quality monitoring is essential for assessing the potential risks associated with water usage. The chosen parameters for our monitoring were based on several criteria, including legislative requirements, environmental relevance, and potential health risks, to provide a comprehensive understanding of water quality and potential environmental and health impacts.

In both seasons, parameters listed in Table 1 were monitored. These parameters were monitored “offline”, in samples taken at the site. List of micropollutants in solid samples differs because these were monitored by different laboratory, which has necessary methodology for these analyses.

Table 1 List of offline analyses performed

Basic parameters	Trace elements	Microbiologic parameters	Micropollutants	Micropollutants in solid samples
BOD ₅	B	Thermotolerant coliform bacteria	Ibuprofen	Over 60 organic substances, e.g.:
COD _{Cr}	Cd	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	2-hydroxy ibuprofen	Bisphenol A
TDS	Pb	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	Naproxen	Carbamazepine
DIS	As	Microorganisms cultivated at 36 °C	Diclofenac	Erythromycine
TOC	Cr	Intestinal enterococci	Paracetamol	Sulfamethoxazole
Conductivity	Cu	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Salicylic acid	Iopromide
N-NH ₄ ⁺	Ni	Potential nitrification activity in soil	Numesulid	Ibuprofen
N-NO ₂ ⁻	Zn	Dehydrogenase activity in soil	Carbamazepine	Diclofenac
N-NO ₃ ⁻	Fe		Carbamazepine-epoxid	Iopamidol
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	Mn		3-hydroxy carbamazepine	Atenolol
P _{tot.}			Gabapentin	Ketoprofen
Mg ²⁺			Tramadol	Metoprolol
Ca ²⁺			Caffeine	Peniciline G
K			Fluoxetine	Sulfamerazine
Na			Estron	Sulfamethazine
SO ₄ ²⁻			17β-estradiol	Sulfapyridine
Cl ⁻			17α-ethynyl estradiol	Trimetoprim
ANC			Estriol	Furosemide
pH			Testosterone	Gemfibrozil
hummus			Sulfamethoxazole	Hydrochlorothiazide
			Trimethoprim	Naproxene
			Chloramphenicol	Triclocarban
			Warfarin	Triclosan
			Potassium acesulfame	Chloramphenicol
			Saccharin	Bezafibrate
			Aspartam	Warfarin
			Sucralose	Saccharin
			Neotam	Gabapentin
			NHDC	Tramadol

5.1 Evaluation of Water Quality for Different Treatment Processes

Biological oxygen demand (BOD₅) remained consistently stable over the two-year monitoring period across all water types. However, the effluent exhibited slightly higher BOD₅ levels (on average, 1.8 mg/L in 2021 and 2.1 mg/L in 2022) than river water (year averages were 1.6 and 1.3 mg/L), even after undergoing UV (year averages 1.6 and 1.4 mg/L) and UF/UV (year averages 1.8 and 1.4 mg/L) treatments. Maximum values in both years were 2.9 mg/L (river), 3.0 mg/L (effluent), 2.0 mg/L (effluent after UV treatment) and 3.8 mg/L (effluent after UF/UV treatment). Nonetheless, all BOD₅ values remained within the legislative limits (≤ 10 mg/L). Overall, the BOD₅ values were stable throughout both years.

Similarly, chemical oxygen demand (COD_{Cr}) values for water after tertiary treatment showed slightly better outcomes than river water. Maximum measured value was in effluent (38.4 mg/L).

Total suspended solids (TSS) also did not exceed any legislative limits (≤ 10 mg/L) in any sample. Maximal values in two years were 9 mg/L (river), 9 mg/L (effluent), 9.1 mg/L (effluent+UV) and 8.0 mg/L (effluent+UF/UV).

Notably, forms of nitrogen and phosphorus were higher in the effluent and effluent after UV and UF/UV than in river water (Table 2). Nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium are essential for plant growth and development. They play a crucial role in the formation of chlorophyll, which is responsible for photosynthesis, and the development of healthy roots, stems, and leaves. The higher concentrations of nutrients in the effluent can, therefore, provide an additional source of nutrients for the plants, which can help promote their growth and overall health, and reduce the need for chemical fertilizers. Moreover, the reuse of wastewater for irrigation can help to reduce the pollution of rivers and other water bodies. By diverting the wastewater to be reused for irrigation, the amount of nutrients and other pollutants that are discharged into these bodies of water can be significantly reduced, which can help to improve their overall quality.

Table 2 Average concentrations (2021+2022) of nutrients

Parameter (mg/L)	River	Effluent	Effluent+UV	Effluent+UF/UV
N-NH ₄ ⁺	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2
N-NO ₃ ⁻	2.5	4.8	5.1	5.1
N _{tot.}	3.2	6.2	6.4	6.0
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	0.1	0.6	0.7	0.6
P _{tot.}	0.2	0.8	0.8	0.6
K	10.0	22.7	22.6	22.9

River water displayed significantly lower conductivity, dissolved inorganic salts, and specific ions (such as Mg, Ca, Cl, or Na) which can potentially lead to soil salinization, especially when applied frequently and for a long time periods.

While river water had on average 16.0 mg/L of sodium, average concentrations in the effluents were 65.4 mg/L in the effluent, 79.8 mg/L in effluent+UV and 70.9 mg/L in effluent+UF/UV. Water hardness was also lower in the river samples (0.9 mmol/L) than in the effluent (2.4 mmol/L), effluent+UV (2.4 mmol/L) and effluent+UF/UV (2.3 mmol/L).

Most of the measured trace elements were below the legislative limits, except for Cd, in both river (0.014 mg/L, in one case in 2021) and effluent (0.015 mg/L, also in one case, in 2022) and Cr (in all four irrigation waters), where the maximum values were surpassed in two cases. The FAO sets the legislative limits for agricultural plants (Cd 0.01 mg/L, Cr 0.1 mg/L); class I of ČSN 75 7143 regulation sets up limit for Cd up to 0.1 mg/L and Cr up to 0.2 mg/L, which were exceeded in both, river and the effluent. However, these concentrations remain suitable for Class II of this regulation. Also, average values were within both regulation limits. It is necessary to point out that although we use FAO regulation for comparison, we do not intend to reuse this recycled water for irrigation of edible plants. Other trace elements were in compliance with corresponding limits.

Microbial parameters in the first year were monitored, however, due to the issue with the secondary contamination by washing water for the UF membrane, they were higher. In the second year, this issue was solved by altering the pilot plant. In maximum values, river water exceeded the limit from the Czech regulation for Thermotolerant coliform bacteria ($\leq 1\,000$ CFU/100mL for Class I) and effluent without treatment exceeded legislative limits as well in several parameters. Both the effluent after UV treatment and the effluent after UF/UV treatment exhibited much better results, and these waters may be classified as Class B of the European regulation (≤ 100 CFU/100 mL). Although both are classified as Class B, the higher efficiency of the UF/UV in comparison with UV alone is obvious from the results (Table 3) - green background is "within the limit", yellow is "Class B/ Class II), orange is "Class D" and red is "Class III/exceeded limit for Class D",

Table 3 Maximum values in 2022

Parameter (CFU/100mL)	Effluent				Relevant regulation
	River	Effluent	Effluent+UV	+UF/UV	
MO cultivated at 36 °C	820 000	6 900 000	760 000	2 320 000	
Coliform bacteria	20 000	310 000	930	580	ČSN 75 7143
Thermotolerant coliform bacteria	19 000	450 000	360	30	ČSN 75 7143
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	10 000	120 000	90	20	EU 2020/741
Intestinal Enterococci	661	64 000	2	1	ČSN 75 7143
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	370	3 200	600	3	
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	400	15 000	96	289	
Classification:	-	-	Class B / Class I	Class B / Class I	

Micropollutants were generally found in higher concentrations in the effluent and effluent after the UV and UF/UV tertiary treatments than in river water. Nevertheless, a few exceptions were noted, where the concentrations of Warfarin, Estrone, Estriol, Acesulfame potassium, and Paracetamol were higher in river water. Tertiary treatment did not show consistent effect on the micropollutant content (Table 4).

Table 4 Average values of micropollutants in 2021/2022

Substance	River	Effluent	Effluent+UV	Effluent+UF/UV
Ibuprofen	LOD	LOD	LOD	LOD
2-hydroxy ibuprofen	66.1	94.1	55.4	96.9
Naproxen	6.9	155.1	117.4	116.6
Diklofenac	107	1045.8	714.3	619.5
Paracetamol	13.7	3.6	20.8	8.8
Salicylic acid	110.1	2469.2	774	198
Nimesulid	1.36	11.2	9.1	7.4
Carbamazepine	54.4	351.1	367.9	376.4
Carbamazepine-epoxid	7.0	60.3	56.1	56.3
3-hydroxy carbamazepine	3.6	54.8	58.5	54
Gabapentin	144.5	1369.3	1285.7	1282.1
Tramadol	123.7	1050.9	1160	1137.9
Caffeine	167.6	1442.7	987.3	1045.5
Fluoxetin	9.4	20.9	22.4	26.4
Estron	3.5	3.5	3.3	3.1
17 β -estradiol	6.1	4.8	4.8	0.5
17 α -ethinyl estradiol	LOD	LOD	LOD	LOD
Estriol	LOD	3.3	LOD	LOD
Testosteron	0.44	0.3	0.3	0.3
Sulfamethoxazol	30.6	538.3	541.4	475
Trimethoprim	14.3	188.4	191.6	185.1
Chloramphenicol	LOD	1.8	33.1	44.5
Warfarin	LOD	18.9	0.1	0.1
Acesulfame potassium	384	373.8	322.6	299.7
Sacharin	8.0	LOD	LOD	LOD
Aspartam	LOD	20.8	LOD	LOD
Sucralose	962.9	19622	20714	19650
Neotam	0.46	3.2	0.4	1.1
NHDC	LOD	LOD	LOD	LOD

5.2 Comparison of Plant Growth and Health across the Four Boxes

Plant growth and health were observed both subjectively - visually on site and via CCTV system. There was no significant difference between the boxes, except the grass treated by effluent had parasites in the 2nd season and needed to be treated by pesticide application.

Trace element analyses revealed that B, Cr, and Fe concentrations were higher in grass irrigated with effluent after 2 years of irrigation in comparison with grass irrigated with river water. Conversely, Zn and Mn concentrations were higher in grass irrigated with river water. However, over the course of the study, some trace elements were found to be present in lower concentrations compared to the initial levels (namely, Cd, Pb, Cr, Ni, Fe, and Mn). The use of tertiary technologies did not result in a decrease in accumulation when compared to grass treated with effluent. In flowers, B, Cu, and Ni concentrations were higher in those irrigated with effluent after 2 years of irrigation, while Cd was of higher concentration in plants irrigated with river water. The concentrations of other elements were comparable. Over the study period, boron and chromium concentrations increased in flowers, while Pb, Ni, Zn, Fe, and Mn content were higher before irrigation. In bushes and shrubs, only Cu and Mn concentrations were higher after irrigation with effluent than with river water. B and Cr concentrations were higher than the initial levels, while the concentrations of other elements were comparable or lower. The decrease in the concentration of elements in plants may be due to the growth of the plants and the spreading of elements throughout the plant mass, or to the release of elements into the soil and/or filtrate.

In Table 5, concentrations of trace elements in perennials before the irrigation and after each season are shown.

Table 5 Trace elements in perennials

	B	Cd	Pb	As	Cr	Cu	Ni	Zn	Mn	Year
	21.4	3.2	3.2	<LOD	4.1	72.0	0.8	49.0	100	
River	35.7	<LOD	1.21	<LOD	7.72	6.9	<LOD	45.3	41.1	2021
Effluent	27.2	<LOD	0.82	<LOD	3.91	12.8	<LOD	42.0	37.1	
Effluent+UV	34.4	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	43.7	26.2	
Effluent + UF/UV	45.8	<LOD	1.11	<LOD	6.72	10.7	<LOD	42.8	47.8	
River	34.0	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	4.59	7.8	0.55	39.7	15.5	2022
Effluent	41.9	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	4.49	11.2	0.57	32.7	22.4	
Effluent+UV	43.4	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	4.96	9.7	0.69	35.7	16.1	
Effluent + UF/UV	47.8	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	4.43	10.3	0.62	43.0	25.0	

Micropollutants in plants were measured before irrigation and at the end of every season. Micropollutants were found to accumulate slightly in plants irrigated by any water source. However, the accumulation observed after irrigation with river water was considerably lower in comparison to that observed after irrigation with effluents and it appeared mainly in the first year of irrigation. Even in the effluents, the accumulation was not significant and typically consisted of concentrations in the range of units of ug/kg of dry matter. The only exception was

tramadol, which was found in concentrations up to 28.9 ug/kg in grass irrigated with effluent. Nevertheless, these concentrations are still considered low. Considering that non-edible plants were used, the associated risk is deemed negligible. Different plants had different general tendencies to accumulate micropollutants: grass accumulated them the most, then perennials, and bushes and shrubs had the lowest tendency for their accumulation. 11 out of 71 substances were found after the first year of irrigation, while after the second year, 10 substances were found. In Table 6, micropollutants before and after two-years period of irrigation which were found in grass are listed.

Table 6 Micropollutants found before and after two-year irrigation in grass (Year 2022)

Irrigation water	River	Effluent	Effluent+UV	Effluent +UF/UV	Before irrigation
Substance (µg/kg DM)					
Carbamazepine	<1.0	4.9	3.5	3.9	<1.0
Ketoprofen	<1.0	<1.0	10.3	<1.0	<1.0
Metoprolol	<1.0	2.8	2.5	3.6	<1.0
Hydrochlorothiazide	<2.0	2.4	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0
Gabapentin	<1.0	6.6	3.5	6.4	<1.0
Tramadol	<1.0	28.9	19.2	20.7	<1.0
Paracetamol	3.6	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0
Carbamazepine-epoxide	<1.0	1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0
Venlafaxin	<1.0	6.9	4.4	5.6	<1.0
Fluconazole	<1.0	5.5	4.7	4.2	<1.0
Sum of concentrations	3.6	59	48.9	44.4	<LOD

5.3 Impact of Irrigation Water on Soil Quality

Humus content in soil was not significantly different in river (9.3 %), effluent (10.1 %), effluent+UV (10.4 %) and effluent UF/UV (9.8 %) from the beginning (11.0 %), however, it was higher in the samples after the irrigation with the effluent. Soil pH slightly changed from 6.74 to 7.58 (river), 7.13 (effluent), 7.48 (effluent+UV) and 7.13 (effluent + UF/UV). As shown in Figure 16, dehydrogenase activity was, overall, higher in the end of the 2nd season.

Figure 16 Dehydrogenase activity (DHA) before and after the two irrigation seasons. 1 = soil depth 0-25 cm, 2 = soil depth 25-45 cm

In Figure 17 Potential nitrification activity (PNA) of the soil sample irrigated with the , the progress of potential nitrification activity (PNA) of bacteria in soil irrigated with effluent is pictured over the whole monitoring period. As in other samples, first there were significant changes, because system is in the shock. Over time, the system comes up to the equilibrium state and changes are moderate.

Figure 17 Potential nitrification activity (PNA) of the soil sample irrigated with the effluent.

Conductivity was significantly higher in the soil after the irrigation with effluent than with the river water, however, this is worst-case scenario due to the use of roofs. In real life, salts would be partly washed out by the rain or snow. Also, conductivity in soil does not entirely correspond to salinization, because soil also contains carbonates and bicarbonates. This can be excluded by analysis of TDS and dissolved inorganic salts, which both showed decreasing the concentrations in soil sample due to washing out the individual salts to the filtrate. On the contrary with dehydrogenase activity, the potential nitrification activity was lower in all the samples. This suggests the shift in microbiome from nitrifiers to another bacterial groups. After the 2nd irrigation season, the soil exhibited lower concentrations of various parameters, including trace elements, due to being washed down to the filtrate (Table 7). Soil samples were taken for each section separately, so the plants in Table 7 refer to the section where the soil was sampled.

Table 7 Concentrations of trace elements in soil before and after irrigation by river and effluent (after 2 years of operation)

		mg/kg DM									
		B	Cd	Pb	As	Cr	Cu	Ni	Zn	Mn	
Before irrigation		23.4	<LOD	18.7	11.9	42.3	27.3	19.4	75.6	420	
After 2 years	River	10.65	<LOD	11.3	8.2	29.5	20.1	15.2	45.1	329	Grass
		16.43	<LOD	15.5	7.2	34.0	20.1	16.7	66.1	311	Flowers
		12.21	<LOD	11.9	7.4	34.6	18.7	17.4	70.3	319	Bushes
	Effluent	10.21	<LOD	11.8	6.6	31.1	20.7	15.7	59.0	343	Grass
		13.73	<LOD	14.3	9.4	38.8	22.5	18.1	70.0	353	Flowers
		13.51	<LOD	12.3	8.1	34.9	19.2	17.4	67.7	319	Bushes

Initially, micropollutants were all below the detection limit, but after both seasons, they were detected at levels measured in units of ug/kg of dry matter. Tramadol was the most prevalent micropollutant in all samples. Interestingly, diclofenac was detected in the first year but was below the detection limit in all samples in the second year. After the first year, 7 out of 71 substances were detected, after the second year, 5 different substances were found in soil samples (Table 8).

Table 8 Concentrations of micropollutants found in soil samples before and after two-year irrigation (G = grass, P = perennials, B = bushes)

Irrigation water	River			Effluent			Effluent+UV			Effluent+UF+UV			Before irrigation
	G	P	B	G	P	B	G	P	B	G	P	B	
Substance (µg/kg DM)													
Carbamazepine	<1.0	<1.0	1.0	<1.0	1.2	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	1.7	1.4	<1.0	1.4	<1.0
Tramadol	<1.0	<1.0	2.2	<1.0	2.4	1.9	<1.0	<1.0	2.1	1.7	<1.0	1.6	<1.0
Venlafaxin	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	1.0	<1.0	1.0	<1.0
Fluconazole	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0	<1.0
Hydrochlorothiazide	<2.0	<2.0	2.1	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0	<2.0
Concentration sum	<LOD	<LOD	5.3	<LOD	3.6	1.9	<LOD	<LOD	4.8	4.1	<LOD	4.0	<LOD

6 Monitoring and Control Systems

The monitoring and control systems for the irrigation boxes were designed to address the pollution distribution from the source water to soil, plants, and filtrate. The systems comprised online and offline measurements.

Online measurements were collected continuously and automatically uploaded to the WIDER UPTAKE project database (WP2) for evaluation according to legislative requirements (Figure 18). The online monitoring system provided data on water quality, soil conditions, and other environmental factors.

Figure 18 Example of parameter readings in a Wider-Uptake database.

Not all probes were available for online measurement, necessitating the use of offline measurements in the laboratory. After the laboratory analyses, these data were manually uploaded to the database and provided additional information to complement the online measurements. Offline measurements included testing for specific contaminants, such as BOD₅, P_{tot.}, micropollutants (e.g., ibuprofen, tramadol), lead, boron, *E. coli*, and other chemical contaminants and pathogens.

6.1 Overview of the Monitoring and Control Systems Implemented

The monitoring and control systems implemented in the irrigation boxes experiment employed a combination of sensors to collect comprehensive data on water quality, soil conditions, and other environmental factors. The sensors used in the experiment included:

- Flow meters: Installed to measure the flow of water from different sources (river water, treated wastewater, disinfected wastewater, and advanced treated water) to each rain garden box.
- Soil moisture and temperature sensors (CS650-DS): Placed in the lawn, perennial, and bush sections of the boxes to monitor soil moisture and temperature.
- Relative humidity and air temperature sensor (RVT13/RK): Mounted on a mast near the container to measure relative humidity and air temperature in the vicinity of the rain garden boxes.
- Turbidity sensors: Deployed to monitor the turbidity of raw water and treated water in the experiment.
- Conductivity sensors: Utilized to measure the electrical conductivity of water, providing information on the water's dissolved salt content.
- pH sensors: Employed to measure the pH of the water, indicating its acidity or alkalinity.

These sensors provided continuous, real-time data, which were automatically uploaded to the WIDER UPTAKE project database for evaluation. The combination of these monitoring devices ensured accurate and comprehensive assessment of the experiment's impact on water quality, soil health, and plant growth, enabling informed decision-making regarding the use of reclaimed water for irrigation. Aside from the parameters, four custom camera systems were set up above the boxes to transmit the daily snapshots of the vegetation to the Wider-Uptake database (Figure 19).

Figure 19 Custom made camera system

The integration and connectivity of the various sensors and devices played a crucial role in ensuring the efficient collection and transmission of data. To establish this seamless connection, a Raspberry Pi was employed as the central control unit, with Home Assistant software installed to manage and coordinate the data collection from each sensor.

The temperature sensors, humidity sensors, soil moisture, and growth-height-measuring sensors (marked with t, h, sm and g on Figure 20) were connected to an ESP8622 microcontroller, which served as an intermediary between the sensors and the Raspberry Pi. The ESP8622 was chosen for its compatibility with the Home Assistant software, its low power consumption, and its ability to support several connected devices. The communication between the four ESP8622 and the four Raspberry Pi (for each box) was enabled through the use of an internet connection, which was established at the site by the research team.

Figure 20 Schematic for sensors in irrigation boxes. The dotted lines designate wireless connection and the black lines denote wires like PoE cables.

The data collection process was designed to be both comprehensive and efficient. Every five minutes, the sensors would transmit their measurements to the ESP8622, which would then forward the data to the Home Assistant on the Raspberry Pi. This frequent data collection ensured the availability of up-to-date information for analysis and decision-making.

In addition to the various sensors, four custom camera systems were strategically installed above the irrigation boxes. These cameras were programmed to capture a snapshot of the vegetation every hour throughout daylight hours, providing valuable visual data on plant growth and health. The captured images were then automatically transmitted to the Wider-Uptake database, enabling researchers to track the progress of the experiment visually.

The use of the Raspberry Pi and Home Assistant in conjunction with the ESP8622 microcontroller and the wide array of sensors allowed for the effective management of the data collection process. The system's design ensured that the data gathered were both accurate and comprehensive, providing a solid foundation for the assessment of the experiment's impact on water quality, soil health, and plant growth. By employing this connected and efficient setup, the research team was able to make informed decisions regarding the use of reclaimed water for irrigation.

6.2 Assessment of Health and Quality Risks

All the measured data were integrated into the database application at <https://database.wider-uptake.eu/> (Figure 21). This platform provided a centralized location for the analysis and evaluation of the experiment's results. The database was essential for the application of the Quantitative Chemical Risk Assessment (QCRA) methodology as well as Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) approach, allowing for a thorough risk assessment of using reclaimed water for irrigation.

The monitoring and control systems employed in the irrigation boxes experiment allowed for the comprehensive evaluation of the safety and effectiveness of using different water sources for irrigation. These systems provided essential data for risk assessment, public reassurance, and informed decision-making regarding the implementation of reclaimed water solutions in urban environments.

Figure 21 Demonstration screenshot of the database application (surveillance timelapse in the middle and measured values graph to the right)

6.2.1 Report Widget

One of the key features of the database web-application is the "Report Widget". The objective of the database application is to streamline the evaluation of recycled water. This functionality will prove useful once circular economy goals are achieved in an EU member state and water recovery becomes widespread. Consequently, users can obtain preliminary assessment results without imposing costly analyses on authorities. The Wider-Uptake database web-application provides this initial data investigation through its "Report" widget.

The "Report" widget features five tabs that process data from the database and use AI to assess the suitability of recycled water usage (Table).

Table9 Tabs of "Report" widget in Wider-Uptake database web-application

Report Widget Tab	Content
End-State Snapshot	The last picture of the process taken at the end of chosen time range if exists.
Measured Values	Data presentation of measured values in line graph form over current time range.
Process Visualization	A visualization of concentrations' distribution over the box layers similar to the one depicted on Figure 9.
Overview of Treatment Plant	Interactive diagram of the plant at the monitoring site.
Risk Assessment	Quantifying chemical and biological exposure risks and probabilities of adverse effects.

The “Report” widget has a certain workflow implemented within. A user can set the timespan of the analysis and what data from that timespan will be displayed (e.g. heavy metals concentrations). In each of the tabs an assessment is available based on the following regulations:

- China National Standard GB T 254999 2010
- EPA Guidelines for Water Reuse
- EU Council Directive 91/271/EEC (Urban Water Treatment Directive)
- EU Council Directive 91/676/EEC (Nitrates Directive)
- EU Parleмент Directive 2013/39/EU (Seveso III Directive)
- EU Parliament Regulation 2019/1009 (Regulation on the Marketing of Fertilizers)
- Regulation 741 (EU) on Water Reuse
- Japan Technical Guidelines for Treated Wastewater Reuse
- Various national directives and regulations from the Czech Republic and Norway.

This commentary is structured around the queried data and provides an exploratory data analysis of the data displayed (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Demonstration screenshot of a process visualization tab in "Report" widget

The same commentary is provided in a risk assessment tab in the widget (Figure 23).

Figure 23 Demonstration screenshot of a risk assessment tab in "Report" widget

6.2.2 QCRA and QMRA

The last step of the «Report» widget in the database web-application and, simultaneously, the last step of the aggregated data processing is Quantitative Chemical and Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessments (QCRA and QMRA). The results of the procedures should let the user know what risks the use of a particular recovered water carry with it expressed as the concentration of the chemical that may possibly get into human body.

QCRA is a probabilistic risk assessment procedure that was created as a reaction to a discovery of Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) that we do not know much about or simply can't detect them efficiently. It broadens the original CRA (Chemical Risk Assessment) that conventionally uses so called conservative point values such as a high exposure concentration, or a lower bound estimate of the health-based guideline level to calculate a deterministic benchmark quotient (BQ) that provides an indication of the risk level. Probabilistic risk assessment replaces those point values by their uncertainty distributions to assess this inherent conservatism and the main source of uncertainty — this is the QCRA (Figure 24).

Figure 24 An illustration describing the difference between a conventional CRA approach and a QCRA procedure. The latter uses dispersions of the parameters rather than fixed values.

In short, the result of the procedure is probabilistic and gives the user a range of possible doses in a particular exposure scenario. QMRA is another established framework for assessing public health risks from pathogenic organisms.

By utilizing these advanced assessment techniques, the database web-application empowers users to make informed decisions about the use of recovered water. Ultimately, these assessments contribute to the ongoing efforts to safeguard public health and promote sustainable water resource management practices.

7 Value Chain Optimization and Resource Efficiency

One of the goals of the project was to demonstrate and describe the ways in which an additional value might be extracted from the CWWTP effluent before the discharge into the Vltava River. While a comprehensive economic analysis was not conducted, the apparent resource efficiency was planned to be assessed by comparing the different irrigation water preparation techniques with the conventional drinking water uptake. In this chapter, we will focus on the principles of the Circular Economy and the broader goals of Wider-Uptake to highlight the potential benefits of using alternative water sources for irrigation.

In the context of this project, using CWWTP effluent for irrigation is a prime example of implementing Circular Economy principles, as it repurposes a wastewater byproduct instead of discharging it directly into the environment. Although our study found that the alternative irrigation water preparation techniques were more expensive than using drinking water, it is essential to consider the broader implications of resource efficiency. By utilizing the effluent for irrigation, we are not only reducing the demand for potable water but also minimizing the wastewater discharge. This approach aligns with the Wider-Uptake goals, which emphasize the importance of adopting innovative and sustainable practices to address pressing environmental challenges.

Beyond the economic considerations, there are numerous environmental and societal benefits associated with employing alternative water sources for irrigation. The use of treated effluent reduces the pressure on freshwater resources, which are already scarce in many regions due to climate change and increasing demand. By decreasing the reliance on conventional water sources, we can contribute to water security and resilience in the face of a changing climate. Moreover, the application of Circular Economy principles fosters innovation and the development of technologies, such as the UF/UV treatment techniques employed in this study. These advancements can lead to improved water quality and reduced environmental impacts, ultimately contributing to the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) related to clean water and sanitation, sustainable cities and communities, and responsible consumption and production.

While our study may not have provided a definitive economic advantage for using alternative water sources for irrigation, it has demonstrated the potential benefits of embracing Circular Economy principles and Wider-Uptake goals. To fully harness these benefits and optimize the value chain, further research and development are needed to improve the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of water treatment technologies. Additionally, fostering partnerships among stakeholders, including policymakers, industry representatives, and research institutions, will be crucial for promoting the widespread adoption of sustainable practices in the water sector. In conclusion, this project highlights the importance of considering resource efficiency and the broader implications of the Circular Economy and Wider-Uptake goals when evaluating water management strategies. By adopting innovative approaches and technologies, we can work towards a more sustainable and resilient future, where the value of wastewater is fully recognized and utilized.

8 Conclusions

This report aimed to investigate the potential benefits and challenges associated with using treated CWWTP effluent for irrigation in an urban environment. The study assessed the resource efficiency and environmental impacts of different irrigation water preparation techniques compared to conventional drinking water uptake. In this concluding chapter, we will summarize the key findings and implications of our study and highlight areas for future research and development.

8.1 Key Findings

Our study demonstrated that it is indeed possible to use treated CWWTP effluent for irrigating plants in an urban environment. The water quality parameters, including biological oxygen demand (BOD₅) and total suspended solids (TSS), remained within the legislative limits across all water types. Furthermore, the treated effluent exhibited higher levels of nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, which can be beneficial for plant growth.

The plant growth and health observed throughout the study showed no significant differences between the four boxes, except for the grass treated by effluent, which had parasites in the second season and required pesticide application. The accumulation of trace elements and micropollutants in plants was relatively low and deemed negligible for non-edible plants. The soil quality was also evaluated, revealing a shift in microbial activity and an increase in salinity after irrigation with effluent compared to river water. However, this is a worst-case scenario due to the use of roofs, and in real-life situations, salts would be partly washed out by rain or snow.

8.2 Implications and Recommendations

The findings of this study demonstrate that using treated effluent for irrigation can be a viable alternative to conventional drinking water uptake. By adopting this approach, we can reduce the demand for potable water in situations where a prolonged life cycle of treated water can be beneficial. To fully harness the potential benefits of using treated effluent for irrigation, it is crucial to ensure the appropriate treatment technologies and infrastructure are in place.

Furthermore, fostering partnerships among stakeholders, including policy-makers, industry representatives, and research institutions, will be essential for promoting the widespread adoption of sustainable practices in the water sector.

While it may initially appear to be easily adoptable and faultless, it's important to note that water recycling is inherently under-investigated to be a universally applicable technique and requires an individual approach. Before using water for irrigation purposes the source of the water should be tested for microbial and chemical risks. In addition, further treatment may be required. During the research the web application was developed in order to help users assess the quality of their recovered water and find ways to safely reuse it.